

Recommended citation: Dubravcic, D., Gillet, D., Holzer, A., Isaac, S., Laperrouza, M., Serikoff, G., Tormey, R., & Vuiliomenet, P. (2017). Curriculum Co-Design Using Participatory Rapid Prototyping Tools . In Quadrado, J. C., Bernardino, J., & Rocha, J. (Eds.), *Education Excellence for Sustainability. SEFI 45th Annual Conference* (pp. 946-953). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Azores, Portugal. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14698330.

Curriculum co-design using participatory rapid prototyping tools

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ABSTRACT

Higher education is experienced by many academics as a highly individualized

environment where they work in relative isolation and often do not see how their teaching fits together with other courses and into the wider curriculum. But, when the ultimate goal of that curriculum is the development of something as complex as engineering expertise, this requires collaboration between teachers across a programme. The goal here was to use low tech rapid prototyping tools in a participatory design approach to involve a range of stakeholders in conceptualizing a curriculum for the teaching of open-ended problem solving and design skills across engineering programmes. The intention was not to prototype the curriculum itself, but rather to use the prototyping process as a means of facilitating collaboration and engagement from across stakeholders. The process undertaken is potentially scalable to other engineering schools and programmes.

Conference Key Areas: *Curriculum Development; Engineering Skills; University-Business cooperation*

Keywords: *Curriculum development; Rapid prototyping; open-ended design projects*

INTRODUCTION

Despite the frequent use of the term academic 'community', higher education is experienced by many academics as a highly individualised environment where competitive promotion and tenure procedures mean that academics often work in relative isolation. One consequence of this is that they often do not see how their teaching fits together with the teaching of others into a wider curriculum picture [1].

At the same time, engineering accreditation bodies such as the CTI or ABET typically require that students are taught the skills of working in teams and in multidisciplinary environments as a core part of the engineer's skill set [2]. Because these skills cannot be taught through a single course but must be developed over time through practice, this in turn requires a coordinated and collaborative approach to curriculum development. Hence accreditation bodies such as the CTI in France or ABET in the US indicate that curriculum decisions should take account of the needs of stakeholders such as students, industry and – perhaps – civil society [3]. How this is to be done, is, however, not specified.

One area of concern in relation to engineering curricula is the teaching of design. It has been noted, for example, that engineering programmes are often heavily weighted in favour of analysis and the solution of closed questions with single correct answers and against the solution of open-ended complex questions that require creativity, interdisciplinarity and group work [4, 5]. There is a certain recursive irony here: some, perhaps many, engineering programmes appear weak in teaching engineering design, while engineering programme teachers often do not participate sufficiently in programme design. This recursive irony can be rethought of as a recursive opportunity: can design tools that are used in creative problem solving be applied to the problem of inclusive participatory curriculum design?

The goal here was to use a set of low tech rapid prototyping kits in a participatory design approach to involve a range of stakeholders in conceptualizing a curriculum for the teaching of open-ended problem solving and design skills across engineering

programmes. In doing so, the approach also modelled industry-university research and development collaboration in that the prototyping kits had been developed in private industry and were being used for the first time in the new context of engineering education curriculum development.

The kits were provided to mixed teams of different stakeholders who needed to discuss with each other their interests and goals in order to construct prototypes relevant to the programme's goals. The intention was not to prototype the curriculum itself, but rather to use the design process as a means of facilitating collaboration and engagement from across stakeholders. The process undertaken and the results obtained are potentially scalable to other engineering schools and programmes.

1 CURRICULUM DESIGN FOR DESIGN AND PROJECT MANAGEMENT

Design has long been identified as the central or distinguishing activity of engineers, and teaching design skills is identified as a key goal for engineering programmes. Engineering design is defined by Dym and colleagues as "a systematic, intelligent process in which designers generate, evaluate, and specify concepts for devices, systems, or processes whose form and function achieve clients' objectives or users' needs while satisfying a specified set of constraints" [6, p. 104]. Design thinking involves a range of different dispositions including creativity, a tolerance for ambiguity, thinking in terms of systems, switching between 'big picture' and 'fine detail' views of an issue, thinking as part of a team, and using several design languages including written, graphical, and mathematical forms of communication. While some of these skills – such as the use of mathematical and formal means of communication – are shared with typical ('analytical') engineering courses, others – such as a tolerance for ambiguity and creativity – are perhaps somewhat different from those found in mainstream engineering courses. Respondents to Kazerounian and Foley, for example, highlighted that that "The typical engineering program teaches that there is a known correct answer that we are aiming toward and that we should find this particular answer as quickly and efficiently as possible" [5, p. 762], a practice that seems out of keeping with the development of design thinking.

Working on open-ended design projects also provides an opportunity for students to learn project management skills. The last few decades have seen significant growth in interest in project management, with professional engineering associations introducing numerous standards and certification processes. Despite this, it has been noted that, "failures to plan accurately and control within "acceptable" limits are commonplace and projects fail at an astonishing rate" [7, p. 304]. Reflecting the importance of project management as an engineering skill, there has been a growing emphasis on group projects as part of engineering education programmes. Ideally, such projects should include explicit training in project management skills. For example, Crawley et al. [8] cite the Linköping University introductory course in Engineering, which accompanies the group project with lectures and seminars that look at the role of the engineer, group process, project management skills, both oral and written communication skills, and accessing and using information. However students will be unlikely to value the above training unless they see it as relevant to their needs and concerns in their current project, which can be difficult given their limited prior experience and typically short project timeframe [9].

There are also numerous approaches to teaching engineering design across curricula. Traditional engineering curricula consisted of an initial period of scientific education

followed by a shift to more engineering-oriented courses. These were typically rounded out with a capstone design course in the final year of studies which allowed students to integrate their learning in a design context. The recognition that this was insufficient to teach engineering design led some programmes to supplement this with a first-year design course, sometimes called a cornerstone course [6]. Others have proposed more radical, curriculum-wide reforms such as those based on Problem-Based Learning (PBL), or the Conceive-Design-Implement-Operate (CDIO) models [8, 10]. Indeed, there is evidence that an integrated programme-wide approach to project management is also desirable [11].

Although widely cited in literature, it is not clear that the CDIO and PBL approaches have had substantial influence in practice. While they argue that a systematic curriculum design process can greatly enhance the chances of promoting effective student learning of engineering skills, Litzinger and colleagues noted that “when we sought examples of engineering programs where effective learning experiences were systematically integrated across an entire curriculum”, they found only a few [12, p. 144].

2 PARTICIPATORY CODESIGN AS A CURRICULUM DEVELOPMENT TOOL

In order to work on building a shared understanding of a programme trajectory for the development of design and project management skills, we adopted a ‘co-design’, approach to building a common sense of the curriculum. The term ‘co-design’ can refer to either a design strategy where complementary components are designed together to provide more feedback loops and interaction between the component designs [13], or to a process in which several different people work together on the design of an artifact [14]. In this paper, we use the term in this second sense. In this approach designers typically involve different stakeholders, but in particular end users, in the design of their artefacts; the idea being to move closer to end-users during the design process.

In the 1970’s several strategies were developed for moving closer to end-users during the design process such as user-centered design (which argues that user concern must be at the center of design decisions), and participatory design [15], (later co-creation, or co-design), which explicitly argued to include the end user in the design process [14]. It has been noted that co-design principles are sometimes pushed by people from business or marketing who see co-design as providing added value to customers [16] rather than by designers. They argue that one reason that has contributed to the slow adoption of co-design is that it requires “that one believes that all people are creative”. As is the case with other bottom-up approaches it also tends to reduce the power of the expert and threatens established power holders.

Indeed, the traditional model was for researchers to analyse users and hand a report of their findings to designers who would create artefacts. In a co-design approach, these roles are blurred. End-users are given a larger role in idea generation, concept development and so on. The role of the researchers and designers in this context is to provide adequate tools to scaffold the ideation and design processes. Research must become facilitators rather than translators of user needs to be given to designers. Designers must “make the tools for non-designers to use to express themselves creatively” and, furthermore, provide expert design skills to the co-design team [14]. Co-design can be used at any stage of product development and some brands are using it to give customers the options at the last stage of design (such as Nike allowing you to change the color of parts of your shoe <http://www.nike.com>). However, [14]

argue for co-creation at the early stage of product design, such as at the moment of idea generation.

Several researchers have investigated co-designing approaches in the context of curricula design [17, 18, 19, 20, 21, 22]. Roschelle and Penuel [18] define co-design as “a highly-facilitated, team-based process in which teachers, researchers, and developers work together in defined roles to design an educational innovation, realize the design in one or more prototypes, and evaluate each prototype’s significance for addressing a concrete educational need.”

However, authors note that “curriculum designers seldom consider the full potential of teachers as co-designers of curriculum materials” [17], even though teachers – as well as students – can offer “critical and constructive perspectives” regarding aspects that make “a lesson engaging and motivating” [17]. Tissenbaum et al. [19] further argue that involving teachers in curriculum design is essential for its success. Penuel and Roschelle [22] argue that co-design is the best way to ensure buy-in by the teachers. This opinion is also echoed by Peters and Slota [20] who find it “essential for helping teachers feel committed to the curriculum.”

Roschelle and Penuel [18] point to a central challenge which is to manage tensions that arise during the codesign process. They find that “managing these tensions led to increased agency on the part of the teachers, increased reflection on their practice, and increased ownership of the resulting design.” Cober et al. [21] argue that in order to achieve the best results, co-design methods should include “support in emergent processes and an atmosphere of trust and inclusion”.

3 CURRICULUM CODESIGN WORKSHOP

Building on some strands of the design philosophies described above, a series of events was conceived to gather different stakeholders in a tertiary education ecosystem to foster collaborative design practices.

The philosophy of the workshops is very much aligned with Schulz et al. [23], i.e. fostering the emergence of innovation in heterogeneous groups through the use of representational methods in a goal-oriented but playful way. It also shares their “manual toolkit-based modeling” approach. The event made use of rapid prototyping kits developed by a design agency (Codesign-it!). The set of tools (“Outdabox”) is made of 6 boxes representing 6 languages:

1. ‘Make Da System’ which makes use of LEGO blocks to allow for systems to be represented in a 3D space
2. ‘Make Da 2D things’ which makes use of various bricolage items for a representation in 2D (scissors, tape, etc.)
3. ‘Make Da 3D things’ which allows 3D prototyping with foam and a hot wire
4. ‘Make Da space’ which permits modeling at the 1/24 scale (very close to Playmobil)
5. ‘Make Da app’ which allows to design the wireframes of an application on a series of whiteboards
6. ‘Make Da movie’ which equips users with a camcorder

These various languages offer different ways to represent a question/issue and, in doing so, allow numerous dimensions to emerge. For instance, participants can collaboratively design a map, a poster, an architectural design, a short video, an interactive ICT tool, or a physical artefact relevant the issue/question and, in doing so participants come to a better and shared understanding of the issue itself.

Under the title “Teaching how to develop creative and practical solutions to real-life, complex, scientific and engineering problems”, the initial workshop made use of the Outdabox tools to address the following questions:

- What skills do students need to learn if they are to successfully deliver creative and practical solutions to real-life, complex problems?
- What means (resources) and paths would best support the development of these skills?

A number of different stakeholders were invited to the workshops, which was attended by 33 people including section directors (i.e., department heads), researchers, lecturers, students, lab technicians, teaching assistants and staff. The participants were each assigned to mixed teams based around one of the boxes/languages and were asked to collaborate on building a rapid prototype. In the first instance each team built a prototype which represented the curriculum vitae of an ideal student. This activity allowed collaborative creation of a shared idea as to what the overall goals of the educational programmes should be, while at the same time gaining familiarity with each of the boxes. In a second activity, the teams chose a set of prototyping tools to represent the pathways and means necessary to aid students in developing these skills.

The workshop gave rise to a number of outcomes:

- A number of participants noted that, unlike traditional meeting formats which do allow for individuals to contribute their opinion, but which often take a conflictual form in which participants argue over priorities etc., the co-design activities – which required participants to collectively produce an artefact – meant that participants had to collaborate and compromise. These were described as being “...yes, and...” conversations rather than “...no, but...” conversations. Working in a design language rather than through a more traditional means of representing the curriculum also meant that the participants were discouraged from getting hung up on debate about specific details (credit weighting, exam formats, etc.) and instead described the overarching curriculum trajectories because these aspects were most directly translatable into these design languages. One participant noted that “it seems a bit strange being asked to play with Lego, but we may never have come up with this if it weren’t for the Lego”.
- A number of participants noted that while they had previously worked as an individual to help students develop design and project management skills, the workshops brought them together with other people interested in the same sets of questions. Furthermore the format of the workshop – which maximized time for interaction and discussion – meant that participants left having built connections with each other. As such, the workshop is the beginning of a process of building a community around this issue within the school.

The approach was not universally popular however, with one participant commenting that he did not have time to play with toys, and another suggesting that the same outcomes could have been achieved in half the time. Another criticism was that participants did not learn any new techniques or pedagogical methods in the workshop.

This workshop was conceived as a first in a series and the goal was to generate ideas and participation rather than to subject the participants’ propositions to rigorous analysis. The need for rigorous analysis is to be picked up in further workshops. This initiative demonstrates a serious yet playful way to build a community while enabling

people to locate themselves and their work within a broader curriculum vision. These boxes/languages provide a rich way of representing and visualizing complex and multi-layered learning experiences.

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